

A Theory of Colour on the Basis of Molecular Strain. Part III. Decomposition of Dyes by the Influence of Solar Radiation.

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In two previous communications by one of the present authors (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1171 ; and Dutt, *this Volume*, p. 99) a general theory of colour on the basis of molecular strain has been elaborated whereby it has been shown that the intensity of colour or the absorption maxima of dyestuffs are in direct proportion to the amount of relative strain contained within the molecule. In this paper an attempt has been made to find out whether the reverse of such a statement will hold good, that is to say, whether the relative strain within the molecules of dyestuffs is in direct proportion to their absorption maxima. And this has been achieved by a direct comparison of their rate of decomposition under the influence of solar radiation.

In a previous paper (Dutt, *this Journal*, *loc. cit.*) it has been shown that amount of relative strain within the molecule of substances can be ascertained by the rapidity with which they undergo decomposition under the influence of various chemical reagents with formation of less strained compounds. Some very simple instances like stilbene, benzylidene aniline, azobenzene, benzophenone and nitrosobenzene were taken and the action of nascent hydrogen on these substances were examined. In each case a hydrogenated, *i.e.*, a less strained compound was formed, and it was found on examination and comparison of the quantity of the resultant products that the amount of calculated strain was in direct proportion to the reactivity of the substances under the influence of nascent hydrogen. Innumerable instances of similar nature can be given in which the conclusions drawn from the foregoing experiments can be applied with success. Looking through the vast number of compounds belonging to organic chemistry, it is almost invariably found that great reactivity or instability means great molecular strain.

Now it has been a well-known fact for quite a long time that the great majority of the dyestuffs under the influence of sunlight tend to bleach away with the formation of colourless products. From the point of view of the theory of colour that has been advanced by one of the present authors, this is a very interesting case in which strained compounds gradually lose their molecular strain under the influence of an external stimulus *i.e.*, solar radiation by the chemical process of either oxidation, reduction, hydration, condensation or hydrolysis. The affair bears some analogy with the detonation of such highly strained compounds as the halides of nitrogen under the influence of compression waves into their elements, or the spontaneous combustion of the highly strained ketons under the influence of sunlight into carbon dioxide and water. When a dyestuff in aqueous solution becomes bleached in presence of sunlight into colourless products, but remains absolutely unchanged in the dark, it becomes quite evident that the sunlight or the radiant energy of the sun acts only as a stimulus to liberate the potential energy contained within the highly strained molecule in the same way as a detonator acts with explosive compounds.

From these it will be seen that the greater the amount of strain within the molecule of a dyestuff, the more easily and quickly it will tend to bleach away into colourless products under the influence of solar radiation. In other words, the more intensely coloured dyestuffs, *e.g.*, the green, blue and violet ones will decompose much more readily than the less coloured ones, *e.g.*, the yellow, orange and red dyestuffs. In fact such expectation has been realised with very few exceptions.* From the experiments that have been carried out in this laboratory it has been found in general that rate of decomposition of dyestuffs is in the following increasing order of magnitude—yellow, orange, red, violet, blue and green. The green, blue and violet dyes are the most fugitive, while the yellow and orange dyes are the most stable.

The total radiant energy of sunlight during the course of these experiments has been ascertained from time to time by the micro-radiometer method, and has been found to remain almost constant,

* The cases of eosin and erythrosin are anomalous probably on account of the large amount of halogen that is contained within their molecule and the ease with which they are liberated in the form of hydrogen halides with consequent decomposition of the whole molecule. The case of acid green (GG) is also anomalous probably due to the great complexity of the molecule and the large area over which the strain is distributed,

the average value being about 4.6×10^{11} ergs per sq. cm. per second. But though of course the figure for the total radiation of the sun is not the same as for the active radiation which is really responsible for the decomposition of the dyestuffs, yet the total and the active radiations must bear a ratio to one another, which must have been constant during the series of experiments that were performed. Hence these experiments were strictly comparative. The following dyestuffs were examined:—

- (1) *Green*—Malachite green, Ethyl green, Bindschedlers green, Acid green, Brilliant green.
- (2) *Blue*—Methylene blue, Indigo carmine, Meldolę's blue, Nile blue.
- (3) *Violet*—Crystal violet, Gentian violet, Methyl violet.
- (4) *Red*—Erythrosine, Safranine, Eosine, Rhodamine, Fuch-sine, Congo red.
- (5) *Orange*—Methyl orange, Orange II, Tropaeoline (OO).
- (6) *Yellow*—Acridine yellow, Uranine, Naphthol yellow, Picric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Specially purified samples of dyestuffs were obtained by successive recrystallisations of the purest available commercial specimens for a number of times until their melting points were constant or there were no changes noticeable in their absorption spectra. Solutions of these dyes in water were made up to a certain strength ($N/10,000$ in most cases) and the solutions exposed to sunlight in air-tight bottles made of specially transparent and colourless glass. The absorption spectra of these solutions during their exposure to sunlight were recorded at regular intervals. The instrument used was a quartz spectrograph of about 5 inches dispersion, a copper arc in conjunction with a 4 inch condenser being used as the illuminant.

In connection with these series of absorption spectra, it should be noted that apart from the absorption maxima, the width of the band is of great importance. In many of the cases the absorption maxima varies but little from the point of exposure to sunlight to that of the complete bleaching away of the dye solution under the influence of solar radiation, while during that interval the width of the band varies considerably. The net effect of sunlight is therefore

practically the same as that of the gradual dilution of the dye solution until its colour becomes invisible. Hence it is apparent that, in general, sunlight decomposes dyestuffs directly into colourless products with very little formation of less coloured compounds having different absorption maxima.

For the sake of convenience the absorption spectra of various dyes in course of their exposure to sunlight have been summarised into tabular forms.

[Figures indicate approximate wave-lengths of absorption maxima.

Figures within brackets indicate the maximum width of the absorption band in Angström units.]

GREEN DYESTUFFS.

<i>Bindschedlers Green.</i>		<i>Malachite Green.</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	7310 (2000)	Before exposure ...	6190 (1900)
10th hour ...	6250 (1800)	20th hour ...	6000 (1650)
20th ,, ...	5875 (1500)	40th ,, ...	5960 (1200)
30th ,, ...	Bleached.	50th ,, ...	Bleached.
<i>Brilliant Green.</i>		<i>Ethyl Green.</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	5250 (3000)	Before exposure ...	6150 (2150)
20th hour ...	6290 (1700)	20th hour ...	6125 (1650)
40th ,, ...	5540 (1300)	40th ,, ...	6050 (1550)
50th ,, ...	Bleached.	60th ,, ...	5850 (1150)
		80th ,, ...	Bleached.
<i>Acid Green.</i>			
	λ		
Before exposure ...	6450 (2350)		
60th hour ...	6075 (1550)		
120th ,, ...	6000 (1450)		
250th ,, ...	6000 (1150)		
350th ,, ...	Bleached.		

BLUE DYESTUFFS.

<i>Methylene Blue.</i>		<i>Indigo-carmin.</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	6650 (3000)	Before exposure ...	6090 (1550)
30th hour ...	6070 (2600)	20th hour ...	6090 (1550)
60th ,, ...	6000 (2000)	40th ,, ...	5550 (450)
75th ,, ...	Bleached.	50th ,, ...	Bleached.

<i>Meldola's Blue.</i>		<i>Nile Blue A</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	6060 (1600)	Before exposure ...	6040 (2250)
60th hour ...	6040 (1500)	30th hour ...	6015 (2200)
120th ,, ...	6040 (1500)	60th ,, ...	6000 (1900)
200th ,, ...	5900 (1000)	90th ,, ...	6000 (1500)
250th ,, ...	Bleached.	120th ,, ...	Bleached.

VIOLET DYESTUFFS.

<i>Methyl Violet.</i>		<i>Gentian Violet.</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	5580 (2010)	Before exposure ...	5650 (2500)
20th hour ...	5510 (1900)	20th hour ...	5450 (2350)
40th ,, ...	5250 (1510)	40th ,, ...	5400 (410)
50th ,, ...	Bleached.	50th ,, ...	Bleached.

<i>Crystal Violet.</i>	
	λ
Before exposure ...	5990 (2440)
20th hour ...	5980 (2300)
40th ,, ...	5580 (2070)
60th ,, ...	5560 (850)
70th ,, ...	Bleached.

RED DYESTUFFS.

<i>Erythrosin.</i>		<i>Eosin.</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	5460 (1530)	Before exposure ...	5210 (1500)
10th hour ...	5100 (500)	20th hour ...	5210 (1500)
20th ,, ...	Bleached.	40th ,, ...	5050 (1100)
		60th ,, ...	Bleached.

<i>Safranine T.</i>		<i>Fuchsine.</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	5250 (1880)	Before exposure ...	5450 (2030)
20th hour ...	5200 (1100)	25th hour ...	5450 (2030)
30th ,, ...	5200 (900)	50th ...	5450 (1980)
40th ,, ...	5150 (800)	100th ,, ...	5300 (1250)
50th ,, ...	Bleached.	125th ,, ...	Bleached.

<i>Rhodamine B.</i>		<i>Congo red.</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	5540 (1250)	Before exposure ...	5240 (2300)
100th hour ...	5580 (1250)	100th hour ...	5240 (2300)
150th ,, ...	5520 (1200)	150th ,, ...	5100 (2000)
200th ,, ...	5280 (980)	200th ,, ...	4850 (650)
250th ,, ...	Bleached.	250th ,, ...	Bleached.

ORANGE DYESTUFFS.

<i>Methyl Orange.</i>		<i>Orange II.</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	5040 (1200)	Before exposure ...	5040 (1200)
100th hour ...	4970 (1050)	100th hour ...	4970 (1050)
450th ,, ...	4850 (950)	300th ,, ...	4920 (950)
650th ,, ...	4850 (950)	700th ,, ...	4800 (700)
850th ,, ...	Bleached.	900th ,, ...	Bleached.

Tropaeolin OO.

	λ
Before exposure ...	5000 (1100)
100th hour ...	4970 (1050)
800th ,, ...	4920 (950)
700th ,, ...	4900 (900)
900th ,, ...	Bleached.

YELLOW DYESTUFFS.

<i>Acridine Yellow.</i>		<i>Uranin.</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	4100 (1100)	Before exposure ...	4940 (1260)
50th hour ...	4100 (1100)	100th hour ...	4650 (840)
100th ,, ...	3800 (500)	150th ,, ...	4600 (880)
125th ,, ...	3800 (500)	175th ,, ...	4600 (800)
150th ,, ...	Bleached.	200th ,, ...	Bleached.

Naphthol Yellow S.

<i>Naphthol Yellow S.</i>		<i>Picric Acid.</i>	
	λ		λ
Before exposure ...	4350 (1450)	Before exposure ...	4200 (1300)
100th hour ...	4350 (1450)	100th hour ...	4130 (1260)
300th ,, ...	4350 (1450)	400th ,, ...	4130 (1260)
500th ,, ...	4100 (1200)	800th ,, ...	4130 (1260)
600th ,, ...	Bleached.	1000th ,, ...	Not bleached.

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